

OPEN PEER REVIEW: Models, Benefits and Limitations

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1 Context

1.1 BACKGROUND

OpenAIRE, the European digital infrastructure for open scholarship, brings together more than 50 institutions to foster and further the implementation of open science across Europe. It is a sociotechnical initiative, comprised of both technical and human support activities. Among the latter, OpenAIRE runs regular workshops to provide outreach, support and training about all aspects of open scholarship, including open access, open data and open scholarly processes. One aspect of OpenAIRE's broad research activities into how openness and transparency can improve scientific processes is its investigation of new models of peer review to literature and beyond.

To further discussion of innovative models of peer review for scholarly publishing, OpenAIRE organized workshop entitled "Open Peer Review: Models, Benefits and Limitations" in Göttingen, 7th June 2016. The Workshop was attended by 71 participants who represented a comprehensive group of stakeholders including publishers, journal editors, interested researchers (as authors and readers), librarians / information specialists, repository managers. A full list of participants (including affiliations) can be found in Appendix A at the end of this document. Short biographical information on the speakers, panelists and moderators see Appendix D.

1.2 WORKSHOP THEME

Digital networked technologies are reshaping scholarly communication, yet the predominant model of peer review remains the one which has been in place since the 1950s. As this model is subject to increasing criticism for being, for example, slow, unaccountable, wasteful of resources, and lacking in incentives, it makes sense to test and examine the ways in which new technologies enable new models of peer review. While a variety of initiatives, led in the main by publishers and researchers, have to date been implemented or proposed, the academic literature around open peer review remains under-developed and the various differing forms of open peer review often ill-defined.

Open peer review (OPR) can be seen as an umbrella term for a variety of ways in which the traditionally closed processes of peer review can potentially be reshaped by networked digital technologies. In response to a variety of critiques of traditional peer review (e.g., that it takes too long, is unaccountable, is wasteful of resources, lacks incentive etc.), different forms of "openness" take shape, including post-publication review, online peer commentary, the publication of review reports as legitimate research outputs in themselves, disclosure of reviewer identities, and so on. These differing forms of openness, designed to address

differing deficiencies in traditional peer review, will in turn be of interest to differing research communities and disciplines. It is perhaps safe to say that no one model of OPR will be suitable for all disciplines.

The workshop aimed to bring together different stakeholders to identify, discuss and work on current and future issues of OPR. Its goals were to critically analyze OPR from a variety of stakeholder perspectives and equip participants with a fuller theoretical understanding of OPR models, a critical overview of the practical implementation of OPR models, raise awareness of the advantages and disadvantages of OPR and the potential links between OPR and open access/open data, the EU's Open Science agenda and institutional and thematic repositories.

1.3 AGENDA

The workshop aimed to inform participants on key current issues in open peer review while also acting as a forum to move this discussion forward. Hence the first half of the day was given over to invited presentations detailing current open peer review activities from Tony Ross-Hellauer (OpenAIRE), Ulrich Pöschl (Max Planck/Atmospheric Chemistry & Physics) and Joshua Nicholson (The Winnower), as well as a structured panel discussion, chaired by Pierre Mounier (OpenEdition) in conversation with Stephanie Harriman (BioMed Central), Alexander Grossmann (ScienceOpen) and Pandelis Perakakis (Open Scholar). The second half of the day was then devoted to interactive break-out groups on three different topics: (1) Varieties of open peer review (moderated by Tony Ross-Hellauer), (2) Engaging stakeholders (authors/reviewers) in open peer review (moderated by Josh Nicholson), and (3) Ethical challenges in open peer review (moderated by Xenia van Edig of Copernicus Publications).

2 Workshop

2.1 WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION

Following a short welcome by Göttingen's University Librarian Wolfram Horstmann, Tony Ross-Hellauer introduced the workshops aims and gave an overview of OpenAIRE's open science activities and especially its work regarding OPR [video]. As Ross-Hellauer explained, in OpenAIRE's definition, OPR is an umbrella concept which covers a host of novel approaches that aim to loosen the constraints of elements of traditional peer review like anonymity, selectivity and opacity. OpenAIRE aims to encourage experimentation in these areas through desk research, stakeholder engagement and through funding small-scale OPR

Open Peer Review, broadly defined ...

Traditionally, peer review is ...

- **Anonymous:** reviewers unknown to authors, or both authors and reviewers unknown to each other
- **Selective:** reviewers selected by editors
- **Opaque:** neither the process nor the reviews are made public

Openness in peer review can refer to ...

- Absence of anonymity (**open identity**)
- Self-selecting reviewers (**open participation**)
- Public processes and reviews (**open access**)

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experiments with OpenEdition, The Winnower and Open Scholar. Regarding the future of OPR, Ross-Hellauer highlighted the possibility of decoupling peer review from the publishing process signaled by the Open

Peer Review Module for repositories (<https://github.com/arvoConsultores/Open-Peer-Review-Module/wiki>) produced as a result of these experiments, as well as the need for standardization of terms in order to bring more clarity to debates about OPR, to assist in the standardization of OPR experimentation and to standardize metadata.

2.2 KEYNOTES

First Keynote: “Multi-stage open peer review integrating the strengths of traditional peer review with the virtues of transparency and self-regulation”, Ulrich Pöschl [\[video\]](#)

Ulrich Pöschl focused on “Multi-Stage Open Peer Review” and how it integrates the strengths of traditional Peer Review with the virtues of transparency and self-regulation.

Pöschl, director of the Multiphase Chemistry Department at the Max Planck Institute for Chemistry and professor at the Johannes Gutenberg University in Mainz, Germany, was an initiator of this approach with the open access journal Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics. While the main dilemma in traditional publishing is often thought to be the necessary trade-off between rapid publication and thorough review and discussion, a multi-stage OPR process can provide both speed and quality according to Pöschl. Rapidly-published discussion

papers offer speedy, citable publication. What Pöschl terms Public Peer Review and Interactive Discussion then offers many of OPR’s benefits such as direct feedback, public recognition, preventing bias, fostering and documenting scientific discourse and so on. Through this approach, argues Pöschl, the final paper maximizes quality assurance and information density. Pöschl ended by offering several thought-provoking ideas for the further development of “Multi-Stage Open Peer Review”, including integration with repositories, living reviews, rankings and tiers, article-level metrics and virtual journals. For more information, see: Pöschl, U., 2012. Multi-stage open peer review: scientific evaluation integrating the strengths of traditional peer review with the virtues of transparency and self-regulation. *Front. Comput. Neurosci.* 6, 33. doi:10.3389/fncom.2012.00033

Second Keynote: “Grey Literature as Open Review”, Joshua Nicholson [\[video\]](#)

Joshua Nicholson’s presentation discussed “grey literature” (e.g., blogs, mailing lists) and social media as platforms for OPR. Nicholson, founder of The Winnower, an innovative open access publishing platform, began by pointing out that there has traditionally been a separation between public venues and scientific ones, where the public is usually excluded from the discussion. This has changed with the advent of social media argues Nicholson,

where discussions via non-traditional channels has enabled a kind of grey literature peer review. Nicholson highlighted the ways in which some research communities came together to discuss and debate research results via social media platforms like Reddit, Facebook and Twitter.

Social media platforms specifically aimed at academia are also on the rise, with commercial platforms like ResearchGate and Academia.edu introducing discussion mechanisms.

Meanwhile, the online journal club PubPeer facilitates post-publication discussion by enabling (open or anonymous) commenting on articles. Nicholson pointed out that we need to find a way to preserve and validate these comments. He then turned to some findings from a Winnower survey (run in conjunction with OpenAIRE) on opinions on peer review,

which showed that most scientists feel they benefit from peer review. Survey respondents reported that they felt making review reports open would not require much more work. The two most important incentives that respondents reported would encourage them to engage in OPR were recognition for their work and whether their peers did the same. The Winnower tries to mix the social, participatory and open elements of social media with traditional publishing type tools like DOI and archiving, making grey literature citable and accessible for the future. Nicholson concluded by making a plea to better use the available infrastructure and furnish repositories with a more attractive design and some of the features of social media to make them more appealing platforms for scientific discussion.

2.3 PANEL DISCUSSION

Panel Discussion: “The Challenges of Open Peer Review”, Pierre Mounier (Chair), Stephanie Harriman, Pandelis Perakakis, Alexander Grossman [\[video\]](#)

Panelists began the discussion by each introducing what they see as the main challenge in OPR:

- Stephanie Harriman (BioMed Central) identified the biggest challenge to be the differing extent to which open peer review is accepted/embraced by communities in different fields and how to best dispel some of the concerns and misconceptions

around open peer review (e.g. no one will agree to review, reviewers won't be able to review honestly if their identities are known). This is compounded by a lack of research into peer review, particularly into the ways in which different models work best for different fields.

- Alexander Grossmann (ScienceOpen) saw the main challenge as that of establishing more openness and transparency in peer review without affecting the quality of scholarly communication. This also includes the question of whether or not the editorial assignment of reviewers is needed to maintain a maximum level of quality.
- Pandelis Perakakis (Open Scholar) focused on the challenges of serving the quality of research, establishing an appropriate level of openness, and developing a public, open source, interoperable and community governed infrastructure

The ensuing discussion was structured around four main topics: (1) defining OPR, publicness and openness, (2) relationship between transparency and quality, (3) OPR and the scholarly communication system, and (4) uptake of OPR in communities & incentivization of reviewers

Theme 1: Defining OPR, publicness and openness

An important challenge for OPR is to properly define it. It is an umbrella term referring to various practices. How can OPR be defined? Under what conditions can an “open” commenting framework be considered as OPR and a peer reviewing process as “open”?

Stephanie Harriman began by pointing out the importance of knowing what people mean by

OPR. While for her it means open reviewer identities, Pandelis Perakakis prefers a more liberal idea of OPR which incorporates openness in time and open participation. This last aspect was picked up by Alexander Grossmann, calling it the “second dimension of OPR”, i.e., being open to all experts to submit

a review, which is completely contradictory to classical peer review, where reviewers are selected by editors. The difference between open peer review and open peer commentary was also seen differently. While Pandelis Perakakis saw the difference to lie in the level of engagement involved (with review making a greater contribution to the article), Stephanie

Harriman acknowledged commentaries as important forms of OPR. Alexander Grossmann pointed out that closed peer reviews can also often be incomplete, resembling commentaries more than full reviews. From the audience, Ulrich Pöschl agreed that there are different forms of review, but sees the contribution to the finished article as a good criterion for distinguishing reviews from commentaries. Another remark by a member of the audience brought up the fact that reviews are usually guided by common rules for procedure and criteria, whereas commentary is freer. Following up on this, Perakakis added that reviews usually end with a recommendation (i.e., to publish, request revisions or reject), whereas commentaries usually require no such thing.

Theme 2: Relationship between transparency and quality

The evaluation of research publications is based on the assumption that anonymity during the evaluation process guarantees the evaluator's neutrality and independence of judgment. How exactly is OPR challenged by that assumption? How can we establish more openness and transparency in peer review without affecting the quality of scholar communication? What are the means needed to achieve it? More specifically: do we need editorial assignment of reviewers?

Alexander Grossmann pointed out that quality assurance is the most important aspect of peer review for most researchers, referring to research that suggests that the majority of researchers who would be willing to review openly expect more quality by openness. In Grossman's own experience across many journals, reviews differ a lot in scope, effort and quality and he is sure that a lot of the low quality reviews would not be submitted in an OPR model. Stephanie Harriman agreed, referring to an experiment: comparing quality of reviewer reports of [BMC Infectious Diseases](#) (OPR) and [BMC Microbiology](#) (CPR) using the "reviewer quality index". A slightly better quality of reviews could be found with OPR (particularly in politeness and substantiating arguments). Stephanie Harriman further emphasized integrity: Although double blind review appears to assess a lot of problems OPR wants to address (removal of biases and providing more objective reviews), since fully double blind reviews are often not feasible (because academic fields are so small that authors will often be identifiable from their style and subject), they become *de facto* single blind reviews. Thus, Harriman considers OPR the best way to answer integrity issues.

Pandelis Perakakis then mentioned two general problems regarding quality assurance in closed peer review that both derive from the fact that closed models strengthen monopolies. Firstly, Perakakis argued that closed review shields highly-ranked journals from scrutiny. They maintain a reputation for high quality peer review, but the general community is unable to verify this as they would be in an open system where review reports were published. Secondly, in a closed model, closed academic circles make decisions about acceptance and rejection, blocking critique from the wider community.

Finally, from the floor, Ulrich Pöschl called for priority-setting to be determined by quality issues when establishing OPR systems: we should consider allowing anonymity for reviewers, as there are still good reasons for keeping this option, and focus on the lowest common denominator, i.e. opening review reports. Jean-Claude Guedon countered that reviews are contributions to the academic conversation and as such should be signed, with reviewers standing by their words publicly.

Theme 3: OPR and the scholarly communication system

At present most of the reviewing process is under the control of publishers, mostly commercial. In fact, it's the most important part of their added value and power over the communication system: they organize (but don't actually do) the evaluation. Services like the Open Peer Review Module (<http://duraspace.org/node/2824>) show a way forward to disentangle peer review from journals/publishers/private platforms, and reorganize it around a next generation of open access repositories with overlay services. What kind of infrastructure is needed, how can we make it sustainable and how could a repository-based author and reviewer reward system work?

Pandelis Perakakis explained that what researchers need is a place to meet and debate each other's works. For him, the internet is the basic infrastructure and communities/societies can organize such meetings themselves. The most important factor is to not build walls around these communities and to allow ample room in the debate for *all* interested experts. Perakakis believes that repositories can provide this space, but that it is crucial to maximize their interoperability in order to centrally connect different infrastructures, e.g. institutional repositories. Such infrastructures can function for relatively little cost in comparison to the current system of scholarly communication.

Stephanie Harriman pointed out that there are already different initiatives that decouple peer review from journals, such as [Peerage of Science](#) and [Axios Review](#), so it is already true that peer review does not necessarily have to happen within journals. However, Harriman emphasized editors' crucial mediational role in ensuring that peer review meets sufficient quality criteria – especially for medical journals which can shape clinical decisions. In addition, she stressed that exciting or buzz-worthy articles will always find willing reviewers,

but there must also be a system in place to ensure that all research receives adequate peer review, regardless of how buzz-worthy.

Alexander Grossmann, however, sees no added value in publishers or journals in the digital age. Both made sense in the time of printed journals, when they organized the printing process and provided the technical interface. The added-services they still offer, like copy- or language-editing, are actually already outsourced. Instead Grossman likes the idea of repositories enriched by an overlay structure that offers communication, quality assessment and discourse to help improve the manuscript (similar to that offered by ScienceOpen).

From the audience, Erik Jan Van Kleef of 1Science.com countered by arguing that such systems have no viable financial models: who will pay for the relevant services in such a system? Alexander Grossmann conceded that there of course there will continue to be costs,

but that these could in principle be covered, for example, by scholarly societies or funding organizations, although such a system would need a sustainable basis. Pandelis Perakakis, however, argued that publishing costs are too often inflated, and that in fact services like typesetting,

copy/language-editing, producing figures and so on are already available outside the publication system. This raised the issue of publishers as service providers: Ulrich Pöschl sees a place for commercial publishers if they reorient themselves as providers of specific, decoupled publishing services.

Theme 4: Uptake of OPR in communities & incentivization of reviewers

One of the biggest challenges of OPR adoption by scholars is the differing extent to which it is accepted or embraced by communities in different fields and how to best answer some of the concerns and misconceptions around open peer review. How can this be improved? Additionally: Why should researchers want to review openly at all? What incentives are there for reviewers to review in the open?

According to Stephanie Harriman, researchers are usually very much against giving up their anonymity to sign their reports. She advocated three pragmatic ways in which to alter this: (1) perform further research on OPR, especially to show its potential to enhance the quality of not only reviews but of the articles themselves; (2) introduce OPR gradually by keeping open identities optional to first normalize the publication of reports; and (3) incentivize reviewers by making them satisfied with the way OPR systems work, but also by enabling recognition or reward. Open review reports enable that reward by allowing reviewers to

gain credit for their work. Alexander Grossmann agreed, as the opacity of the work done in closed review systems can act as a disincentive – some reviewers don't invest effort in their reviews because that work cannot be proved. Making review reports more open and citable

would be a great step forward in incentivizing reviewers. Grossman also mentioned the possibility of paying reviewers, which he considers infeasible due to the actual cost of the expertise involved. Finally, Pandelis Perakakis called for a shift in our way of thinking about peer review: it shouldn't be seen as the reviewer doing someone a favour. Rather, reviewers should choose to review an article because they believe they can improve its quality. For Perakakis, there is no better incentive than being recognized by your peers and bringing new quality to research.

3 Breakout Groups

The second part of the workshop consisted of interactive discussion groups, designed to build on themes discussed earlier in the day by allowing all participants to engage in deeper discussion. Three different topics were open for discussion over two sessions, with each participant able to join two groups. Each group was chaired by a moderator who introduced the discussion themes. Participants then discussed structured questions in sub-groups before reporting back their opinions to the group. Participants were further asked to define new questions for the second group. In the next session, the second group was given an overview of the opinions of the first group and invited to build upon or disagree with them, as well as being asked to address the new questions defined by the first group. The themes for the breakout groups were: (1) varieties of OPR, (2) stakeholder engagement in OPR, and (3) ethical challenges in OPR. For the full lists of questions see Appendix C. Each breakout group was assigned a notetaker (Emilie Hermans, Frank Manista and Arvid Deppe), whose extensive records of each discussion have been used to provide the summary and conclusions given here.

3.1 BREAKOUT GROUP 1: VARIETIES OF OPR

As addressed in the earlier panel discussion, the first challenge that OPR presents is to ensure that when we talk about OPR we are talking about the same aspect(s), whether open identities, open reports, open participation, or other aspects. Is there a minimal definition of openness in peer review? The idea of this group was to make one step towards a deeper understanding of what OPR can be and how the heterogeneity can be (intellectually, terminologically and practically) handled. It aimed to

- Try to develop a joint understanding of peer review, open peer review and the differences between them
- Bring together different forms of OPR and discuss them in their particularities, benefits and drawbacks
- Increase sensitivity for the heterogeneous nomenclature of OPR variants and identify the most crucial ambiguities

Q1: What is Peer Review?

Participants defined peer review as a community process of quality control/assessment most closely associated with journals, but also applicable to monographs, grant applications and so on. Communities consist of people with an expertise in a given area. This expertise need

not be just a matter of qualifications but also experience and hence peers are not limited to academia. Peers could also come from other practitioners in the field (industry), secondary education (teachers specializing in certain topics) or citizen scientists. This conversation then led to consideration of what quality assurance means. Participants argued that quality control in peer review means helping to improve an article and/or identify mistakes, but also a filtering function to help define what is important. This leads to the question of whether peers are really equipped to determine the significance of a piece of research. Finally, since it decides whether something should be part of the scientific dialogue or not, peer review also includes an aspect of power. One participant noted that peer review is also defined by its process and the control it exerts over the process of academic publication.

Q2. What is Open Peer Review? What forms of OPR (and what forms of openness) can you identify?

Originally presented as two questions, the groups decided to answer these questions together. Open peer review was very roughly defined as being peer review with any “open” processes. The answers to what is or should be open were as heterogeneous as the field of OPR itself, and included concrete ideas like openness after the process, open discussion, open reviewer identities and possible interaction (“comment on the comments”). It also provoked questions about whether we meant openness to the author or to the public, openness of all the comments or just the decision letter, and openness during or after the peer review process. Some groups saw open identities of reviewers as crucial to the

definition of OPR. Still others saw openly published reviews as a minimal characteristic, but another did not consider it necessary to disclose everything in a review, but only those aspects needed to see how a decision was reached. There was also an emphasis on open participation and the crowdsourcing of comments – OPR drew repeated comparison to websites like Airbnb or TripAdvisor. Finally participants noted that OPR should not be defined in isolation as it is only one part of a wider scholarly communications ecosystem. Other elements that participants felt should be included in a definition of OPR were citeable reviews, portable and cascading peer review, review of reviewers, pre/post-publication review, filter vs. feedback functions, and the openness of process versus the openness of results.

Q3. What forms of OPR do you think are the most important?

Participants agreed that there are many different forms of OPR which address different needs for differing communities. The most important criteria are that OPR should ensure scientific accuracy and produce good science. Additionally, there were two new beneficial aspects of OPR mentioned here: the educational benefit of transparent, open access processes for young researchers and the machine readability of review outputs/metadata.

Q4. Which forms of OPR could make peer review worse in your opinion? Why?

Participants voiced concern about the potential for unconfirmed/unreviewed results to be cited prematurely as a result of post-publication review. Unreviewed scientific results might find their way into the media, to be misunderstood or misused and thus cause hysteria (for example in medical research). But one participant countered this argument by saying that the media would learn that pre-prints are not reviewed and thus not to be reported. This participant continued that in fact, such episodes of media hysteria can in fact educate the public to be skeptical about scientific results, to come to see that the scientific method is not infallible. Another major concern voiced about open identity OPR was the potential for early career researchers to risk a backlash from more senior researchers should they criticize them publicly. OPR also has the potential to be abused by, for example, “gaming the system” (authors reviewing their own or friends’ work) – although it was pointed out that although this might be true of an open participation system, where reviewers were self-selecting, it would not be true of an open identity and/or open reports system where reviewers would have to stand publicly by their words. Finally, coming back to open commentary, there was a fear of losing quality control standards due to social media-like commenting fields (“anarchy in commenting/decisions”).

3.2 BREAKOUT GROUP 2: STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT IN OPR

Attempts to open identities or publish review reports go against a well-established system and hence often face mistrust, lack of interest or active resistance. This breakout session therefore sought to better understand the roles, motivations and fears of authors and reviewers, and to discuss ways to engage authors and reviewers in Open Peer Review processes. It aimed to discuss different functions and importance of mediation, understand what motivates author/reviewers to join OPR processes and to discuss incentives and arguments for participation in OPR.

Q1. How important do you think (e.g., editor) mediation is in OPR? Why?

All groups considered mediation very important to support authors, reviewers and their interaction. Participants felt that support should not be limited to initiating and managing the interaction itself, but also giving technical help and advising on difficult situations such as guiding authors how to handle contradictory reviews. Additionally, mediation can include questions of ethics, solving conflicts or filtering comments on highly contentious topics. There was some suggestion that mediators should also ensure quality control, but this was deemed controversial and others argued that it is debatable whether this classical editor function is still required in OPR. Nevertheless, participants noted that the need for mediation shall vary depending on the discipline and the type of content under review (results, data, software etc.). Finally, there was some suggestion that some of the mediation currently

done by editors might be better achieved by automation (e.g. automatic selection of reviewers via citations), authors and/or the community.

Q2. What possible incentives can you think of to engage reviewers?

Groups agreed that OPR potentially poses extra work for reviewers and might be more time-consuming than classical peer review. It therefore stands to reason to offer incentives for reviewing openly. Most suggestions were based on the idea of rewarding reviewers, financially or symbolically. This could be simply by offsetting reviewer work with contributions towards author article processing charges (APCs) for their future publications (as is currently done by [PeerJ](#), for example), or even by formally transferring APCs to RPCs (review processing costs). Another idea put forth was the potential to have funders/institutions officially contribute towards payments for review work to individuals or institutions. However, others felt strongly that the current system of social incentives should not be undermined by financial ones.

Social incentives relate to career rewards focusing on recognition, promotion, acknowledgement, and so on. Recognition might be granted via altmetrics or informally via a social media. It was noted that such systems benefit from, if not require, persistent identifiers like ORCID, DOI etc. Such credit systems also have an aspect of the “gamification” of peer review. Other possible motivations mentioned were social pressure to review as well as policies/mandates by government or funders (as is apparently the case in Sweden). Open Reviews would also simplify collaborative review (where many reviewers each review a different section), which again reduces work for each reviewer. One participant argued that since OPR might be seen as an incentive itself, the focus should be on tackling the obstacles rather than creating new incentives.

Q3. What concerns do you think authors might have about OPR? Which argument could help against these fears?

The groups identified the fear of being criticized publicly as the main impediment for authors, spurred on by fears of “washing dirty laundry in public” and the “abuse of power dynamics”. Further issues were the fear of having to share the limelight with reviewers making major points and of losing control over the – potentially never ending – peer review process. Finally, authors in OPR may miss the prestige of coming through the review process of a highly ranked journal. On the other hand, reviewers might also be afraid of being accused in public of making flawed criticism or misunderstanding a paper, and this may be a huge disincentive – especially for early career researchers. There were no particular arguments made against these fears. Participants’ preferred strategies seem rather to be to emphasize the benefits of OPR for authors, such as more constructive, less judgmental reviews and the chance to interact, improve and thereby produce better science.

Engagement accordingly needs education in OPR through good information and dissemination activities. It is especially about working on politeness and building trust, making OPR understood as a “chance to improve your work” or, more generally, changing the culture of review.

Q4. Do you think different disciplines will vary in their attitudes towards OPR? How?

Discussions brought up a lot of disciplinary differences that participants think need to be taken into consideration when thinking about OPR. First of all disciplines seem to differ ideologically in their attitude towards openness in general, and so perhaps disciplines which are open or hostile to Open Access will hold similar views towards OPR. Further,

there are differences in, for example, sensitivity to time taken, publication models, the culture of rejection (e.g. in medicine it is normal to have high number of rejections), special processes (e.g. scooping is a concern where research can be copied easily) and reviewing effort (science is easier to peer review than humanities). Disciplines also differ in size, which can have different effects. In small communities for instance researchers often know each other in person which may be problematic. On the other hand, small close-knit communities may foster a greater sense of duty. Participants were of one voice that despite these differences, OPR is possible for every discipline; it may just need different implementations. Therefore tests of implementing OPR should start with specific disciplines – preferably those most open to and experienced with openness and transparency.

3.3 BREAKOUT GROUP 3: ETHICAL CHALLENGES OF OPR

A lot of the arguments made against closed peer review are of an ethical nature: reviewer bias, difficulties with authors/reviewer anonymity, opaqueness or subjectivity of reviews and even the question of whether any review was done at all. The differing forms of OPR may seem to address many of these problems, but it is no panacea. The idea of this group was to raise awareness of the ethical problems that OPR can raise and discuss ways of tackling them. It aimed to identify the most pressing ethical issues, discuss ethics in OPR in response to concrete challenges and to find suitable solutions, with a special focus on ethical considerations concerning early career researchers.

Q1. What in your opinion are the most pressing ethical issues in the context of OPR?

Participants felt that ethical concerns around OPR encompassed diverse aspects. First of all, with open identity peer review, there is the question of whether it is of higher ethical priority to let the author know who is judging him or not to force the reviewer to reveal his identity. Another aspect is the possibility of disadvantages for authors. For instance, does rejection at one journal foster hasty judgement and influence the chances of gaining acceptance at another journal. One participant noted that the first opinion stated in a public discussion can often inordinately influence the direction of the ensuing discussion. Although participants recognized that there might be potential conflicts in some specific cases where reviewer and author identities were open, it was generally agreed that radical transparency would solve more problems on the whole than it would produce. Another important issue is that OPR opens the door for potentially unethical behaviours. In post-publication OPR, for instance, if an author's ideas are made public in advance of full publication, others might appropriate those ideas without giving due credit. Another scenario concerning open commenting platforms is reviewer identification. How can we be sure a person is who they claim to be? In addition to these questions of how to formulate new workflows and codes of conduct for new ethical issues raised by OPR, participants emphasized the need to communicate the ethical benefits of OPR.

Q2. Consider this case: An author is unhappy with a very critical pre-publication OPR. He/she demands their work be withdrawn from the process and the OPR taken offline completely. Would you agree to the author's demands? Why/why not?

Groups' opinions tended to depend on the circumstances but the dominant answer was that in such a situation, openness should prevail:

- The answer would be NO if the content of the review were considered fair scientific discussion. Additionally, it needs to be considered that the controversy might be interesting for the future development of science – controversy often attends radical ideas, but radical ideas push science forwards. It was concluded that the point of OPR would be missed completely if only positive reviews were allowed to be open.
- The answer could be YES if there were no scientific benefit/interest in keeping the review available. This could be the case for unscientific discourse or personal/insulting comments. Special consideration could also be taken to protect young researchers.

Furthermore the answer would naturally depend on the specific conditions of the peer reviewing process. One participant suggested that a solution to this problem could be to invite another independent reviewer to give a new point of view. Participants were clear

that this case and the discussions around it show the importance of (1) a code of conduct, including an explicit statement and even legal agreement that provides clarity on the conditions under which the OPR will be conducted for author, reviewer and editor, and (2) the need for ongoing human mediation in OPR.

Q3. What ethical concerns do you have about (1) editors selecting reviewers, (2) authors selecting reviewers?

The groups agreed that editors usually have too little knowledge of specific sub-disciplines to choose reviewers with a maximum of competence in the field. Authors, on the other hand, know their peers but may be biased in their choices. A solution could be an algorithm-based selection. Most ideas of solving or reducing the problem focused on transparency and self-regulation: as OPR opens the whole reviewing process, conflicts of interest can be identified, biases can be recognized and arguments can be scrutinized by community. This can be supported by additional oversight measures such as the review of reviewers. If the reviewing system is participatory or based on self-selecting reviewers, the problem of selection would of course disappear, although replaced by new specific challenges.

Q4. Are there special issues to be considered regarding young researchers?

Participants raised several ethical issues that specifically affected young researchers. First of all, young researchers might be afraid of publicly criticizing senior researchers, fearing

negative consequences for their careers. On the other hand, seniors might be worried young researchers might not review to their standards of critique. Although young researchers might bring a fresh perspective, have more time and be more motivated and precise in their reviewing, they may not have enough experience to fulfil the task. This may be seen as a problem when reviews are open, but on the other hand, OPR can also work as an educational tool for young reviewers on reviewing, reviewing processes and potentially on ethical issues as well.

4 Outcomes, recommendations & lessons learnt

Discussion across all areas showed that variety and experimentation are key to the success of open peer review. Participants were in broad agreement that the differing kinds of OPR have a lot of potential to improve peer review, but they were also united that no one model will fit all disciplines or overcomes all obstacles. Therefore different OPR initiatives and approaches are to be welcomed for the shared goal of producing better science through openness and transparency. Let a thousand flowers bloom, so to speak.

Yet as these variants crop up, it is important that we are able to distinguish readily between them, and to recognize what actually works in which contexts. The heterogeneity of views on what OPR is that occurred during the workshop just drive home the fact that we need a better overview of the different models, including perhaps agreement on what minimum levels of openness are necessary to categorize a process as open, and – most importantly – a common, community-agreed taxonomy of OPR should be developed.

OPR is a process which involves many different stakeholder groups. The workshop showed that the unease of some reviewers, authors and editors toward OPR is legitimate and must be faced with evidence of its effectiveness and advocacy regarding its benefits. This will be helped by efforts to reward the work of peer review (but “socially” via citation credit and such rather than financially). Introducing OPR requires cultural change, which is notoriously difficult. Participants were of one voice, however, that OPR is possible for every discipline; it may just need different implementations. Therefore tests of implementing OPR should start with specific disciplines – preferably those most open to and experienced with openness and transparency.

On the ethical side, it is clear that OPR is no panacea and that while it may resolve some ethical issues regarding accountability and bias with classical peer review, it nonetheless poses new problems. Discussions indicated the importance of agreeing on common ethical rules and committing them bindingly. Our workshop participants generally agreed that OPR promises to improve peer review, and made plain that its ethical benefits – transparency, accountability, openness – should be made a key part of arguments in its favour.

To draw general conclusions, we can say:

- OPR processes need to be made transparent and comparable.
- A common terminology is needed as a basis of comparing (effectiveness of) OPR models.
- Different modes of mediation need to be tested.
- Ways to acknowledge and reward reviewers appropriately need to be found.
- Development of mandates and policies should be supported.

- Differences and particularities of disciplines must be acknowledged and taken into account.
- A common code of conduct should be created, especially taking into account the needs of young researchers.
- Binding agreements regarding the terms of OPR procedures for authors, reviewers, editors and publishers should be in place ahead of time.

5 Documentation

All keynotes and the panel discussion were recorded. The videos are available at:

- <https://vimeo.com/channels/openaireworkshop6>

The slides of all presentations can be found at Slideshare:

- http://www.slideshare.net/OpenAIRE_eu

Photos of the workshop are available on Flickr:

- <https://www.flickr.com/groups/openaire>

Further documentation:

- Workshop announcement and programme on openaire.eu:
<https://www.openaire.eu/events/eventdetail/388/53|54|55|56|57|58/workshop-open-peer-review-models-benefits-and-limitations>
- Workshop report on blog.openaire.eu: <https://www.openaire.eu/open-peer-review-models-benefits-and-limitations>
- Workshop report on openaccess.si (Slovenian): <http://www.openaccess.si/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/28-Porocilo-Odprto-recenziranje-13.6.2016.pdf>
- Workshop report on BioMed Central blog:
<http://blogs.biomedcentral.com/bmcblog/2016/06/15/challenges-open-peer-review/>

6 Appendix

APPENDIX A – PARTICIPANTS LIST

Name	Institution
Angelaki, Marina	National Documentation Centre, Greece
Arning, Ursula	ZB MED, Germany
Assinen, Pauli	University of Helsinki, Finland
Camilleri Vella, Josianne	University of Malta, Malta
Ceseviciute, Ieva	Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania
Deppe, Arvid	Göttingen University, Germany
Dickel, Julia	Stiftung Tierärztliche Hochschule Hannover, Germany
Eichler, Frederik	FU Berlin, Germany
Eiteljoerge, Sarah	Göttingen University, Germany
Eskevich, Maria	Radboud University, Netherlands
Galea, Joelyn	University of Malta, Malta
Gargiulo, Paola	Cineca, Italy
Grossmann, Alexander	ScienceOpen GmbH, Germany
Gurinovich, Roman	CONZL OÜ, Estonia
Görögh, Edit	University of Debrecen, Hungary
Hafner, Georg	Göttingen University, Germany
Harriman, Stephanie	Biomed Central, United Kingdom
Heber, Joerg	Nature Communications, United Kingdom
Hermans, Emilie	Ghent University, Belgium
Hoffman-Sommer, Marta	University of Warsaw, Poland
Hoffmann, André	Universität Zürich, Switzerland
Hornig, Christoph	Germany
Jones Nelson, Alissa	De Gruyter, Germany
Kacherki, Umeshreddy	Indian Institute of Science Education & Research, Pune, India
Kluyver, Thomas	University of Southampton, United Kingdom
Kosanovic, Biljana	University of Belgrade, Serbia
Koskinen, Kimmo	University of Helsinki, Finland
Kotar, Mojca	University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
Koukounidou, Sylvia	University of Cyprus, Cyprus
Kuchma, Iryna	Stichting eIFL.net (EIFL), Lithuania
Larsen, Asger Væring	University of Southern Denmark, Denmark
Linde, Peter	Blekinge Institute of Technology, Sweden
Loizides, Fernando	University of Wolverhampton, United Kingdom

Manista, Frank	JISC, United Kingdom
Marti, Zafiro	University of Cyprus, Cyprus
Medves, Maud	Inria, France
Mimkes, Julika	University of Göttingen, Germany
Montenegro, Eva	FECYT, Spain
Mounier, Pierre	CNRS CLEO EHESS, France
Nicholson, Joshua	The Winnower, United States
Oberländer, Anja	University of Konstanz, Germany
Perakakis, Pandelis	University of Granada, Spain
Pöschl, Ulrich	Max Planck Institute for Chemistry, Germany
Príncipe, Pedro	University of Minho, Portugal
Rank, Sven	Göttingen University, Germany
Ross-Hellauer, Tony	Göttingen University, Germany
Rozenberga, Gita	University of Latvia, Latvia
Schirrwagen, Jochen	University of Bielefeld, Germany
Schuller, Dorothea	Göttingen University, Germany
Sipria-Mironov, Elena	University of Tartu, Estonia
Stojanovski, Jadranka	University of Zadar, Croatia
Stone, Graham	United Kingdom
Tate, Dominic	University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom
Tautkeviciene, Gintare	Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania
Tavares, Richard	PRACE AISBL, Belgium
Tennant, Jon	ScienceOpen, Germany
Thorsteindottir, Solveig	Landspítali Univ Hospital, Iceland
Tiggre, Antanina	Belarusian State University, Belarus
Tkacikova, Daniela	VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Republic
Tobias, Regine	KIT Scientific Publishing, Germany
Valikonytė, Dalia	Vilnius university, Lithuania
van Edig, Xenia	Copernicus GmbH, Germany
van Kleef, Erik Jan	1science, Belgium
Van Nieuwerburgh, Inge	Ghent University, Belgium
Verdicchio, Dirk	Universität Bern, Switzerland
Weilenmann, Anne-Katharina	Switzerland
Wennström, Sofie	Stockholm University, Sweden
Wintz, Elise	Germany
Woutersen-Windhauer, Saskia	University of Amsterdam, Netherlands
Šimukovič, Elena	University of Vienna, Austria

APPENDIX B – DETAILED PROGRAMME

09.00	Registration
09.30 - 09.40	Wolfram Horstmann: Welcome
09.40 – 10.00	Tony Ross-Hellauer (OpenAIRE) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop aims; overview of Open Peer Review and OpenAIRE
10.00 - 10:30	Keynote 1: Ulrich Poeschl (ACP): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-stage open peer review integrating the strengths of traditional peer review with the virtues of transparency and self-regulation
10.30 - 11.00	Keynote 2: Josh Nicholson (The Winnower): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grey Literature as Open Review
<i>11.00 - 11.20</i>	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:20 - 12:40	Panel Discussion: The Challenges of Open Peer Review <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Panel participants: Pierre Mounier (Chair) (Open Edition), Stephanie Harriman (BMC), Pandelis Perakakis (Open Scholar), Alexander Grossmann (Science Open)
12.40 - 13.40	Lunch
13.40 - 14.50	Moderated Breakout 1 (parallel sessions) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Varieties of OPR • Stakeholder engagement in OPR • Ethical challenges of OPR
<i>14.50 - 15.10</i>	<i>Coffee Break</i>
15.10 - 16.00	Moderated Breakout 2 (parallel sessions) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Varieties of OPR • Stakeholder engagement in OPR • Ethical challenges of OPR
16.00 - 17.00	Reporting back and final discussion

APPENDIX C – LIST OF QUESTIONS (BREAKOUT GROUPS)

Varieties of OPR (Moderator: Tony Ross-Hellauer)

1. What is peer review?
2. What is open peer review?
3. What forms of OPR can you identify?
4. What forms of OPR do you think are the most important?
5. Which forms of OPR could make peer review worse in your opinion? Why?

Stakeholder engagement in OPR (Moderator: Joshua Nicholson)

1. How important do you think (e.g., editor) mediation is in OPR? Why?
2. What possible incentives can you think of to engage reviewers?
3. What concerns do you think authors might have about OPR? Which argument could help against these fears?
4. Do you think different disciplines will vary in their attitudes towards OPR? How?

Ethical challenges of OPR (Moderator: Xenia van Edig)

- What in your opinion are the most pressing ethical issues in the context of OPR?
- Consider this case: An author is unhappy with a very critical pre-publication OPR. He/she demands their work be withdrawn from the process and the OPR taken offline completely. Would you agree to the author's demands? Why/why not?
- What ethical concerns do you have about (1) editors selecting reviewers, (2) authors selecting reviewers?
- Are there special issues to be considered regarding young researchers?

APPENDIX D – BIOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION

Alexander Grossmann studied Physics in Aachen and holds a PhD from the Research Center Jülich. He worked for several publishers (Wiley-Blackwell, Springer, de Gruyter). He is Professor of Publishing Management at HTWK Leipzig University of Applied and Co-Founder of ScienceOpen.

Stephanie Harriman is the Medical Editor at BioMed Central and has a degree in Medicine from Brighton and Sussex Medical School. She is also co-Editor-in-Chief of Research Integrity and Peer Review.

Pierre Mounier holds Masters in Classical Studies and in Anthropology from Sorbonne and Nanterre University. He is research engineer at the School for Advanced Studies in the Social Sciences (Paris, France) and associate director of the Center for open electronic publishing (Cléo).

Joshua Nicholson received his PhD in 2015 from Virginia Tech studying the role of the karyotype in cancer initiation and progression in the lab of Dr. Daniela Cimini. In addition to his work on the bench he has authored numerous articles on scientific funding and publishing. He is CEO and Co-founder at The Winnower “The Winnower”, an open access online scholarly publishing platform that employs open post-publication peer review.

Pandelis Perakakis has a PhD in clinical psychophysiology from the University of Granada, Spain. He works as a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Granada and is co-founder of Open Scholar CIC that he currently serves as director. Open Scholar is an organization of 120 volunteer research scholars from 17 different countries that actively promote an open model of scientific evaluation and dissemination.

Ulrich Pöschl is director of the Multiphase Chemistry Department at the Max Planck Institute for Chemistry and professor at the Johannes Gutenberg University in Mainz, Germany. His current scientific research and teaching are focused on the effects of multiphase processes in the Earth system, climate, life & public health. Pöschl is actively engaged in the promotion open science, and is the initiator of interactive open access publishing with public peer review and interactive discussion (multi-stage open peer review) as established with the international scientific journal Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics (ACP, <http://www.atmospheric-chemistry-and-physics.net>) and the European Geosciences Union (EGU, <http://www.egu.eu>).

Tony Ross-Hellauer is Scientific Manager for the OpenAIRE2020 project at Georg-August-University Göttingen. He has a PhD in Information Studies (University of Glasgow, 2012), in addition to MA (Philosophy) and MSc (Information and Library Studies) degrees. He is an enthusiastic advocate of Open Access and Open Science whose research interests include repositories, metadata, and the philosophy/history of technology.

Xenia van Edig, PhD in Agricultural Sciences, is responsible for Business Development at Copernicus Publications, the largest open access publisher in the Geo- and Earth system sciences and known as one of the first publishers to embrace public peer review.